

PHILOLOGY

TRENDS OF LANGUAGE LEARNING IN UKRAINIAN REFUGEES

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Abstract

Ukrainian war refugees abroad are having to study several languages at a time. Their changing language needs are examined by looking at real-life examples. New trends are identified, based on the analysis.

Keywords: language learning, ESL, EFL, linguistics.

The Russo-Ukrainian war has triggered a mass exodus of people from Ukraine. Many people evacuated out of fear either to the Western part of the country or abroad while some had no choice but to leave their home, being threatened by a possible occupation.

Since many people ended up in foreign countries virtually overnight, the question of language learning has become of prime importance to them. A majority of them are faced with a daunting task of adapting to a different language environment and the strain induced by studying sometimes several languages at a time.

Few scientific articles have dealt with the issue of language learners and refugees and asylum seekers. There are hopes that this article might draw attention to the problem and spark further discussion.

The article seeks to examine how language needs of Ukrainian refugees change by unpicking real-life cases.

We will be examining the experience of five people, all of them being people who in one way or another had or chose to move out of Ukraine. These people are aged 16-35 and are of different social and financial statuses, with some still receiving benefits and some receiving them until quite recently. For the sake of privacy they will be referred to by the initial letter of their names.

The first case is that of V. who after moving out of Ukraine lived in Poland and is now residing in Germany. After moving to Poland she picked up some Polish but didn't take any language courses or tutoring in that language, Polish being quite easy for Ukrainians at least when it comes to some simple everyday needs. Currently she is residing in Germany and has been taking German intensive courses, striving to achieve B2 level. As far as English is concerned, V. has been studying it actively for three years twice a week but has switched to only a lesson a week, the latter being prompted by acquiring a job and her German courses taking the better part of her time. In the time span mentioned, her command of English has improved significantly. That said, one has to note that the level of German interference has increased so much so that her initial utterances might start with or be completely in German of which she is cognizant but still has trouble controlling it. One ventures to assume that learning German has positively contributed to her being quite masterful in different verbal structures like the passive, compound tenses, and modal verbs + have + past participle, the latter in both passive and active forms. One

may attribute it to German and English having similar tense systems. She finds it hard to switch between the two languages quickly and so far has found the necessity of speaking in German the whole day rather taxing. V. has little time for home assignments in English so her studying of the language is mostly limited to that lesson a week.

The second case is that of R. who after moving out of Ukraine and living for some time in the Netherlands, is now residing in the Czech Republic. He did not study Dutch while in the Netherlands and neither is he studying Czech. He is being tutored in Hungarian for personal reasons. He has been having English lessons twice a week, has shown good progress and has no interference from other languages. R. is diligent and studies a lot of flashcards, reads original books. Despite having a sizable vocabulary he has a hard time choosing proper word forms. He also speaks to a native American speaker once a week for the sake of practice. His case differs in that he puts a lot of time and effort into studying outside the classroom as it were.

The third case is that of Y. She has a similar path to that of V. in moving to Poland first before ending up in Spain. She had been having two lessons a week before switching to one lesson and shortly discontinuing studying altogether, given her enrolling in a Spanish language course and starting a job. Her progress was steady with some time for homework.

The fourth case is that of E. He is living in the Netherlands. At first he had been reluctant to study Dutch but ultimately had to start it due to a lack of prospective job opportunities otherwise. His English is at a nice level of fluency with accuracy leaving a lot of room for improvement. Initially, he would have 2-3 lessons a week but later switched to one due to the Dutch language courses. It is hard to judge his progress given the fact that too little time has passed; he does little to no home work outside lessons, giving a preference to listening to podcasts.

The last case is that of J. He has repeated the same path as the other two people mentioned here, first moving to Poland and then to Austria. He used to have two lessons a week. His English is conversational, although there is some dissatisfaction with the ability to express oneself. He has not taken any language courses in the language of the country but at the same time has been entertaining the idea of enrolling into a language course. The fact that he has not yet chosen a country to settle in for good stands in the way of his committing

to language studies of the language of his future country of residence.

This review lets one make the following observations:

- 1) A majority of refugees and asylum seekers from Ukraine is mostly likely to live in more than one country abroad before settling for good;
- 2) Many of them will be studying both English and the language of a country they will be residing in;
- 3) English is the first thing to take a dent when commitments start adding up, *eg* a new job or some major change in lifestyle;
- 4) Most people do little to no homework which can hamper progress and increase the chance of students being dissatisfied and abandoning studies altogether.

Based on these observations, one can conclude that refugees are experiencing a tremendous strain in terms of time, mental energy, and willpower to sustain their studies. For some it proves too much and makes them opt for less study time, both in and out of class. One believes it calls for a system where students are able to engage in some language learning on the fly as it were, meaning they do not necessarily have to have a proper language learning session. These could be some

assignments specifically tailored for every student in the form of audio or short materials for revision. This very well may offset language decay and if done correctly may lead to improvement.

Such language learners will definitely benefit from a short overview of learning strategies and the fact that consistency plays a crucial role in such processes.

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